

DURABILITY OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Fiber reinforced materials (composites) are considered very seriously for use in primary loadbearing structures. However, the pace at which they will actually be introduced into the structural designs of the future very much depends on the solution of a critical problem, which is our inability to predict the long term behaviour of the material in a given service environment. The research and development of integrity evaluation and life-time prediction schemes for composite materials is thus a burning issue. The information, which we intend to present, is part of an ongoing program which is directed toward and accelerated determination of the endurance limits of composite materials. Real-time testing is simply not feasible because enough integrity has to be designed into composite structures such that they have a service life which is often as long as twenty or thirty years.

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge on durability of composites is of key importance for anyone who needs to make decisions on the use of these materials in lightweight loadbearing structures.

In-service failures of resin-matrix composite laminates, as well as bonded joints, are obviously the endpoint of an evolutionary process. This process is driven by the degrading influences of the service environments such as high temperature, moisture, radiation, etc.

The degradation processes act slowly : for example, water vapour, even in coastal areas would need years to completely soak a sixteen ply graphite-epoxy laminate. Creep deformation at moderately low temperatures obviously act on the same time scale.

Modern structures usually need to be guaranteed for a service life, which gives the environmental influences plenty of time to degrade key mechanical properties such as tensile and compressive stiffness, tensile and compressive strength, shear strength, fracture toughness, etc. Commercial airplanes for example are designed to fly safely for 90 000 hrs, distributed over a thirty year service life. The replacement of some parts will, of course, always be necessary in order to maintain the required safety standards but the main airframe is expected to last for the total projected period, which includes, landings and takeoffs in widely different climates.

The work that we will report is part of an ongoing program to study the combined effects of moisture, temperature and stress on the structural integrity of polymers and composites. The program is directed towards the identification of parameters which affect the materials performance in later phases of the composite structures operational life.

The main objective of this paper is to illustrate experimental findings in the areas of creep deformation and moisture absorption and to bring out a conceptual model that is useful to bring these information islands together in a framework that also contains concepts of physical aging.

EXPERIMENTALLY OBSERVED CREEP RESPONSE

A series of creep and creep-recovery experiments on graphite-epoxy (T300/934) at the different temperatures revealed an unexpected stiffening behaviour slightly above 100°C. The creep compliance transverse to the fiber direction was modeled with a power law :

$$D_{22}(t,T) = D_0(T) + C(T) t^n \quad (1)$$

The power law exponent n was found to be independent of temperature [1]. The temperature dependence of D_0 and C is plotted in Fig's 1a and 1b below.

Fig. 1a. Instantaneous transverse compliance as a function of temperature.

HYGROTHERMAL BEHAVIOUR

The nature of the moisture absorption process can yield important information on the composites microstructure such as the configuration and the flexibility of the molecular chain in situ, the morphology of the polymer, etc. Adamson [3] reviews a number of sorption anomalies which were identified as a result of such careful fundamental studies.

The water molecules leave the environment at the surface of the glassy polymer or composite. Their basic transport mechanism is provided by the kinetics of the polymer molecules, which carries them deeper into the polymer network. The "speed" with which this transport mechanism operates is measured macroscopically by the diffusion coefficient.

Changes in the environmental conditions, such as an increase in temperature correspond to an increase in the mobility of the polymer molecules (at least below T_w). Such an increased mobility provides a "faster" transport mechanism which is measured macroscopically by an increased diffusion coefficient.

We derived [4] simple equations for the prediction of through the thickness moisture distributions $m(z,t)$

$$m(z,t) = m_s \left(1 - \frac{z}{3.36 \sqrt{D_z t}}\right) \quad \text{for } t < t_1 \quad (2)$$

$$m(z,t) = m_s \left\{1 - \exp\left[-.218\left(\frac{t}{t_1} - 1\right)\right] + \exp\left[-.218\left(\frac{t}{t_1} - 1\right)\right] \left(1 - \frac{z}{h}\right)^2\right\} \quad (3)$$

for $t > t_1$

with

$$t_1 = 8.85 \cdot 10^{-2} (h^2/D_z) \quad (4)$$

with m_s = saturation value

$D_z(t)$ = diffusion coefficient (in the thickness direction).

The total water uptake $M(t)$ (mass increase of the composite laminate) is given by the equations below :

$$M(t) = 1.12 M_s \frac{\sqrt{D_z \cdot t}}{h} \quad t < t_1 \quad (5)$$

$$M(t) = M_s \left\{1 - \frac{2}{3} \exp\left[-.218\left(\frac{t}{t_1} - 1\right)\right]\right\} \quad t > t_1 \quad (6)$$

The dotted line in Fig. 2 was obtained on the basis of equations (5) and (6) and compared with the solid line, which is a prediction of moisture uptake based on the Fickian diffusion model

Fig. 2. Comparison of moisture uptake based on different diffusion models.

The horizontal axis in Fig. 2 represents a nondimensional time t^* defined as

$$t^* = \frac{D_z \cdot t}{(2h)^2} \quad (7)$$

The internal variable model that resulted in equations (5) and (6), can easily be extended to cases for which there is simultaneous diffusion in the x, y and z directions of the composite laminate [4]. The main advantage of the model is nevertheless that it is based on the theory of Lagrangian thermodynamics which has been advocated over the years by M.A. Biot [5]. The theory provides an excellent framework which we can use to derive evolution equations which describe the deformability (viscoelastic deformation) of resin-matrix composites under the simultaneous action of mechanical stresses and environmental influences such as heat and moisture. In the next paragraph we give experimental evidence that the set of evolution equations needs to be rooted in the molecular structure of the resin matrix.

AN EXTENDED FREE VOLUME MODEL

The view that the free volume at the glass transition temperature should be a constant (one fortieth of the occupied volume) was first introduced by Fox and Flory [6]. In Fig. 3 we plotted the variation of free volume as a function of temperature

Fig. 3. Variation of free volume with temperature.

We can clearly distinguish three regions :

- 1 = truly glassy region
- 2 = physical aging region
- 3 = rubbery (or WLF) region.

The increase of free volume with decreasing temperature which occurs in the "truly glassy region" (region 1 in Fig. 3), is somewhat unusual. Nevertheless, the circles represent actually measured values [7]. The mechanism which is proposed is a significant decrease in molecular mobility below T_ω . A possible source is intermolecular hydrogen bonding. The experimentally observed data were obtained on TGDDM-DDS epoxies to which family the 934 and 5208 resins belong. The increase in free volume reflects the inability of the occupied volume (specific volume) to expand and contract at the same rate as the occupied volume. The molecular mobility below T_ω is so low that the free volume remains essentially frozen into the structure.

The stiffening in creep response which we observed in Fig. 1b thus occurs above T_ω , in the physical aging region, where the free volume is a minimum. Apparently, some of the available mechanical deformation energy is required to counterbalance effects of excess free volume below T_ω .

Above T_{ω} all of the applied force is seen as elastic-like deformation.

This current free-volume model also allows to provide the necessary mechanism for the low temperature transition T_{β} which has been observed at -50°C . The accumulated free volume at T_{β} is sufficient to allow a Crankshaft rotational motion of the glycidyl portion of the epoxide group in TGDDM-DDS-epoxies.

Failure phenomena, such as fracture, impact strength, longterm-creep and creep-rupture, which at first may seem to be distinct phenomena, thus represent the ability (or lack of ability) of a polymeric chain to change configuration at some particular rate.

CONCLUSIONS

Environmental degradation processes which limit the durability of resin-matrix composite materials can be captured in a framework of Lagrangian thermodynamics. The evolution equations, which result, should be rooted in the physics of the polymer network interaction. A conceptual extended free volume model for such interactions was presented.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Dr. Howard Nelson and the other members of the NASA-Ames Test Engineering and Analysis Branch for providing them with a most stimulating research environment.

Prof. H.F. Brinson stimulated the research and provided support for the first author through the NASA-Ames Virginia-Tech Summer Faculty Program.

Special thanks are due to Myriam Bourlau for her excellent typework.

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